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DIGITAL LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS TO RAISE ENGINEERING STUDENTS' ACTIVE PARTICIPATION AND UNDERSTANDING: USE CASES OF SOCRATIVE, MATLAB GRADER, AND KAHOOT SOFTWARE IN MECHATRONICS EDUCATION

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In the Mechatronics department of Fontys University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, the problem exists that the students do not do their homeworks that are given during the lectures. This constitutes a setback when the teachers want to continue their lectures covering new topics, especially when these new topics are linked to the previous topics. Interaction with the students during the lectures becomes inefficient too, because they lack the previous knowledge. This kind of a problem is often seen in Engineering Education and the participants of the workshop have experienced that in some way. A simple solution would be to divide a bigger course into several parts, where each part has to be finalized with an exam (summative examination), before the new part starts. The alternative of it (formative examination) which purely aims for indicating the current learning outcome of the students without the exam being officially graded. Homework and lecture interaction are good examples of formative exam if the student gets feedback on his/her answers.

In this workshop the use cases, tips and tricks will be presented using some online tools that are experimented with in Control Engineering lectures. These software tools called Kahoot, Socrative, and Matlab Grader will be compared with each other and examples will be presented from Control Engineering lectures that are applicable to other disciplines. The participants will use those tools and they are expected to solve mini-quizzes using these tools as if they are the students. This will follow to brainstorm and discussion sessions on how should the questions be formulated by the teacher so that the students get the maximum understanding out of it. Below is a summary of the three tools that will be covered during the workshop.

Socrative is an online quiz tool with handy options to summarize the results if the homework assignments are implemented in a closed-ended question form (i.e. multiple choice) in this tool. The teachers will be encouraged to put their homeworks into this system and copy the students' results each week into a logbook which is shown to the class in the beginning of the lecture to trigger the competition feeling besides accentuating how important the homework is. As an exercise the participants will be

set in groups to formulate a mathematical problem into a closed-ended homework question making sure that the students follow the steps to solve the mathematical problem from A to Z instead of coming up with the correct answer in any other alternative (easier) way.

However, Engineering courses have often open-ended final exam questions and that's why the homework assignments which should support the examination type are also expected to be open-ended. Matlab Grader is an automatic student work grader that provides feedback on the code that students submit. This tool requires more development time before first time use during the course period but saves much time when implemented once, compared to manually grading the programming assignments. Use cases will be presented on how to convert from easy mathematical operations to difficult Control Engineering homework material to Matlab Grader assignments that are automatically graded by the tool and sends feedback to the students on which part their implementation has failed. The software checks the code on the basis of functional programming where each functions' input must yield a certain output. For example if the student needs to write a function (an algorithm) for the mathematical operation 'addition', a test case would be inputting 3 and 5 to check if the outcome is 8. If the outcome is not 8, the student is informed that 3+5 does not yield 8 in his implementation. This presentation will be followed by a work session where more complex problems are worked out into test cases where the participants aim to cover the possible alternative algorithms a student can come up with.

As a third browser-based software, Kahoot is a more informal and fun quiz tool to be used at the end of the lectures when students are tired of being exposed to new information. It creates a competition environment where students strive for answering fast and correctly at the same time. The participants are first going to get a feeling of a Kahoot quiz as if they were students and striving for the highest point in the competition. Then an interactive discussion will follow where in Engineering Education can Kahoot fit in order to add more activating work forms in the courses.

The participants will be encouraged to use them via demonstrations to show that these tools require little time during the lecture period if set up once.

As a take-home message, examples, digital attachments and tips will be given based on my own experience on how to construct such homework systems and which tool is suitable for what type of education. A discussion about how to define some additional homework rules to increase student participation in the lectures is relevant and will be held if time permits. It is expected that the participants go back to their school with new ideas and motivation to make their courses more fun, activating and diverse. That's why the topic suits to the conference theme 'Diversity in Engineering Education' to great extent.